

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR INCREASING THE SPEED OF RUNNING FOR SHORT DISTANCES

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Annotation: Increasing the effectiveness of competitive activity in sprinting requires a comprehensive approach to the development of a methodology for sports training of sprinters, based on identifying and taking into account the mechanism of formation of the speed of running steps, as well as pedagogical conditions that contribute to the growth of sportsmanship of athletes.

Key words: athletes, sprinting, individual technique, pedagogical approach, methodology.

Introduction. In sprint, the actions of an athlete are considered as a system of rationally organized movements aimed at increasing the effectiveness of competitive activity [1, 3]. The complexity of running 100 and 200 meters is due to the need to perform a large number of various movements arising from one another and creating optimal conditions for subsequent ones, which contributes to the development of maximum speed [2, 4, 5]. The technique of sprinting has a clearly oriented individual character, due to a complex of various factors [7, 8, 10].

According to B. B. Boborakhmatov, during the development and improvement of speed and speed-strength qualities that determine the speed of running, it is necessary to take into account the mechanism of interaction of external and internal forces [6]. External forces are understood as: gravity, support reaction force, friction force, resistance force of the external environment. Internal forces are represented by muscle tension, distribution and redistribution of muscle efforts [9, 11].

The speed of an athlete is determined by the activity of not only the peripheral motor apparatus, but also the central mechanisms of movement control, which, along with motor centers, include vegetative and sensory centers [12, 13]. Therefore, outstanding results are achieved by sprinters with a high level of coordination in the work of complex mechanisms for controlling motor acts located at different levels of the central nervous system, provided that optimal indicators of the development of speed-strength qualities, body stability, and coordination of movements of the upper and lower extremities are achieved.

In the process of formation and improvement of individual running technique, it is necessary to create conditions for the athlete to realize the semantic essence of movements in their integrity, which ensures an effective solution of the task [14, 15, 16]. As the level of development of motor-coordinating qualities increases, the parameters of running steps improve, the individual running technique of a sprinter undergoes significant changes by:

- optimization of the length and frequency of running steps;
- rationalization of placing the foot on the support;
- increasing the force and speed of repulsion from the treadmill;
- improvement of running straightness [17, 18].

An analysis of the specialized literature has shown that so far there is no unity in understanding the ideal technique of running steps over short distances; in addition, used as the main exercises aimed at increasing the strength and speed of repulsion from the support, they do not always correspond to the structural content of the sprinter's running steps [21, 22]. This requires the search for new approaches to improving the individual technique of sprinting, taking into account the athlete's predisposition to this type of sports activity. Thus, one of the signs of an athlete's psychological readiness for self-realization and self-improvement through the systematic performance of running exercises similar in structural content is the ability to objectively assess the prospects for their own growth in sportsmanship in terms of details that characterize the improvement in the parameters of the running

steps technique, which ensures an increase in competition results and forms satisfaction with the training and competitive activity [19, 20].

The formation of the skill of coordination of the individual rhythm of the first movements of the runner with the signal of the starting pistol is one of the important pedagogical conditions for optimizing the running steps. To solve this problem, it is advisable to fix the rhythm of giving commands to start running at competitions of various scales, compare and analyze their time characteristics in order to establish a general pattern [4, 6]. This will allow to determine the features of the methodology for the formation of an individual motor rhythm of motor acts performed from the starting blocks.

Identification of the features of placing the foot on the support allows you to determine the possibility of controlling this type of movement, which is of great importance for the use of additional reserves to increase the speed of running steps. The content of the methodology we developed provided for the possibility of correcting the placement of the foot on the side track. If changing the way of interaction with the support did not require significant neuromuscular efforts and the sprinter could slightly turn the toes outward, then in accordance with the individual program for improving the technique of the leading parameters of running steps, the athlete focused on the possibility of improving the straightness of running by applying special methodological techniques; decrease in the amplitude of body oscillations in the lateral or anterior-posterior direction.

In the experimental group, we used the methodology developed by the authors for managing and correcting the individual technique of qualified sprinters. Before the start of the pedagogical experiment, testing was carried out in order to identify the initial level of physical and special running fitness of athletes in the control group and the experimental group. The following control exercises were used: running 30 and 60 meters from a high start; run 1000 m; standing long jump; shot put (4 kg) with the right and left hand.

Processing of the obtained data did not determine significant differences in the level of physical fitness of athletes from the CG and the EG ($p>0.05$). To identify indicators of special running preparedness, the following were used: running for segments of 150 m; 200 m; 250 m; 300 m; five-time long jump running 1000 m. Analysis of the study materials also did not reveal significant differences in the level of special running preparedness of sprinters from the CG and the EG ($p>0.05$).

To identify the degree of formation of the individual technique of the leading parameters of sprinting: the consistency of the runner's actions at the start with the judge's teams; optimal arrangement of parts and links of the body in space during the starting acceleration; running straightness. Special evaluation criteria have been developed. Thus, the degree of coordination of the athlete's movements with the referee's commands at the start was assessed by: the optimal position of the body, head, upper and lower limbs in accordance with the command "to start"; rational change in the position of parts and links of the body on the command "attention"; timeliness of the first steps of the run (in points).

Criteria for evaluation:

5 points - the ideal arrangement of parts and links of the body on the starting blocks in accordance with the height and weight indicators of the athlete. Full consistency of the exit from the start with the shot of the starting pistol;

4 points - rational arrangement of parts and links of the body on the starting blocks with minor correction before the starting shot. Timely start of running steps;

3 points - measuring the starting blocks from several attempts, a slight delay in the reaction to the shot of the starting pistol;

2 points - adjustment of the location of parts and links of the body to the command "attention". A significant delay in the reaction to the shot of the starting pistol;

1 point - errors in the location of parts and links of the body on the starting blocks; inconsistency of the first steps with the sound of the starting pistol.

Analysis of the study materials did not reveal significant differences in the degree of formation of individual technique of the main parameters of the running steps of

athletes from the CG and the EG ($p>0.05$). After the end of the pedagogical experiment, repeated testing was carried out to identify the dynamics of physical and special running fitness indicators of sprinters from the CG and the EG, as well as the degree of formation of individual technique of the leading parameters of running steps.

Analysis of the obtained results indicates that the improvement occurred in both groups: the CG and the EG, however, in the runners from the EG, the increase in indicators was significantly higher. So, with the initial data in the 30-meter run from a high start in the CG of 4.18 ± 0.06 s, by the end of the pedagogical experiment, the results improved and amounted to 4.01 ± 0.07 s ($p>0.05$); in the EG, respectively, with initial indicators of 4.19 ± 0.09 s, the data increased and amounted to 3.87 ± 0.10 s ($p>0.05$). With the initial data in the 1000 m run in the CG $3.07.2\pm 0.13$ m, by the end of the pedagogical experiment, the indicators improved and amounted to $3.04.9\pm 0.15$ m ($p>0.05$); in the EG, respectively, with initial results of $3.07.1\pm 0.16$ m by the end of the pedagogical experiment, the data improved and amounted to $3.01.7\pm 0.11$ m ($p>0.05$). A similar tendency to improve results in the EG was also revealed in other tests.

Conclusions. Thus, the results of the pedagogical experiment showed that the problem of increasing the speed of running over short distances should be solved in a complex way, taking into account the fact that the speed of running steps is a function of the whole organism. When looking for additional reserves to improve speed when overcoming a competitive distance, it is important to identify the mechanism for increasing the speed of movements; take into account the predisposition of the athlete to this sport; identify the pedagogical conditions for increasing the speed of running steps; build the training process in accordance with the individual characteristics of the runners.

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